

Solitary Confinement and Human Rights: A Healthcare Provider Handout

Healthcare provider (HCP): any licensed professional who provides healthcare for individuals who are detained in isolating conditions of confinement (often referred to as solitary confinement)

- WHO?** Patients experiencing incarceration
- WHAT?** Solitary confinement & isolation
- WHEN?** Throughout and after isolation
- WHERE?** Medical clinics in carceral settings
- WHY?** Beneficence, non-maleficence
- HOW?** Care, collaboration, reform

The **United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners** (aka the Mandela Rules) and **Canadian court rulings** citing the **Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms** have called for a significant decrease in the use of isolation or solitary confinement.

The **College of Family Physicians of Canada (CFPC)** called for the abolition of isolation or solitary confinement in a 2016 position statement.

Isolation, segregation, seclusion, structured intervention units, separation, and cellular/close/separate/solitary confinement are some of the terms used to describe a form of confinement where people are separated from others inside a carceral facility and held alone in a confined space. **Solitary confinement** refers to any confinement of prisoners for 22 hours or more a day without meaningful human contact, and with limited or no access to rehabilitative programs.

Locking individuals in a confined space for most of the day, sometimes for weeks, occurs by many mechanisms:

- Lockdowns
- Restrictive movements
- Isolation for medical or psychiatric observation
- Disciplinary or administrative separation, etc.

Negative Health Effects of Isolation	
During Isolation	After Isolation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased risk of self harm and suicide • Exacerbation of mental illness • Emotional hypersensitivity • Cognitive dysfunction • Paranoia • Hallucinations • Insomnia • Palpitations • Weakness • Hostility • Worsening of chronic conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased rate of recidivism • Increased rate of future violence • Increased all-cause mortality • Increased risk of death from non-natural causes (suicide, violence, drug overdose, accident)

"For those sentenced to imprisonment, the punishment is the deprivation of liberty. It's not an opportunity for further abuse and punishment. ... [solitary confinement] is extremely, extremely damaging."
 - Justice Louise Arbour

Key Human Rights Documents

Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms

- Protects basic rights and freedoms essential to maintaining democracy in Canada
- Rights and freedoms guaranteed in the Charter dictate how governments act, and how laws and policies are interpreted
- Healthcare providers should be familiar with Section 12 (Cruel and unusual treatment or punishment)

UN Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (The Mandela Rules)

- Apply to health providers working in Canadian carceral facilities
- Inform the Canadian Medical Association Code of Ethics
- Healthcare providers should be familiar with rules 23 (Exercise and sport), 24 to 35 (Health-care services), 36 to 46 (Restrictions, discipline and sanctions) & 47 to 49 (Instruments of restraint)

UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights

- Sets out fundamental human rights to be universally protected
- Recognizes the foundation of freedom, justice and peace as respect for the equal and inalienable rights of all humans
- Healthcare providers should be familiar with Articles 2, 5-9, 29 & 30

The following are adapted from the 2025 practice standard published by the BC College of Physicians and Surgeons

HCPs should recommend removal from isolating/solitary conditions of confinement when:

- The person's physical and/or mental health is negatively impacted
- The person has an existing and symptomatic mental health condition
- The person has been held in isolation for 22 or more hours per day for 15 or more consecutive days

If the isolating/solitary conditions continue, HCPs should recommend providing meaningful human contact for more than two hours each day

HCPs should regularly assess the patient's environment for potential negative impacts to their health including (but not limited to):

- Overall sanitation of the cell
- Irregular temperatures
- Lack of access to proper nutrition
- Cleanliness of clothing and bedding

Document any concerns in the patient's medical record and recommend that those concerns be addressed

Healthcare providers should be **aware of, identify, document and offer to treat** the mental and physical health implications of isolating/solitary conditions of confinement.

Special Populations

- Indigenous
- Immigration detention
- Youth
- Mental illness
- Women
- Black
- Trans & non-binary
- Physical or intellectual disability

See full toolkit for further info

HCPs should report, in writing, signs of torture or cruel treatment to a higher legal or medical authority

If working in Provincial facility

Responsible physician

Investigation and Standards Office

Minister of Health

Minister of Public Safety

If working in Federal facility

Institution's Chief of Health Services

Office of the Correctional Investigator

Minister of Health

Minister of Public Safety

Important Documents referenced above:

- General Assembly resolution 70/175, United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (the Nelson Mandela Rules), A/RES/70/175 (8 January 2016), available from <http://undocs.org/A/RES/70/175>
- The United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (the 'Nelson Mandela Rules') A/RES/70/175. Available at: https://www.un.org/en/events/mandeladay/mandela_rules.shtml#:~:text=A%2FRES%2F70%2F175%20not%20only%20adopted%20the%20revised,the%20course%20of%20his%20struggle
- The United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights (10 Dec 1948) Available at: <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>
- Treating Incarcerated Patients in Isolation. Practice Standard. College of Physicians and Surgeons of British Columbia. April 14, 2025 (Version 1.0). <https://www.cpsbc.ca/files/pdf/PSG-Treating-Incarcerated-Patients-in-Isolation.pdf>